

ORGANIZATIONAL PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF EDUCATION OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE INCLUSIVE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *It is stated that inclusive education is an opportunity created for children with disabilities to receive education together with their healthy peers.*

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Today, the new image of Uzbekistan is in sync with the positive changes in the field of education.

In our country, a number of reforms are being implemented in the education of children with disabilities based on the advanced trends of the world. Among them, the legal basis for the protection of children's rights was created, a number of laws, decisions and decrees were adopted, and children's rights were guaranteed in them.

Convention on the Rights of the Child, adopted on November 20, 1989, Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-4860 dated October 13, 2020 "On measures to further improve the system of education for children with special educational needs", Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-4312 dated May 8, 2019 "Concept of development of the preschool education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", In the Law "On Education" approved on September 23, 2020, "Inclusive education aimed at ensuring the equal right of every child to education, preventing any discrimination and discrimination", In one norm of Chapter 9, Article 50 of the Constitutional Law "On the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan", which entered into force on May 1, 2023, "Inclusive education for children with special educational needs in educational organizations and education is provided, Chapter 2, section 2.4 of the "First Step" state curriculum approved on February 4, 2022 states that "Education and upbringing process for children with special educational needs is inclusive education and special education implementation of measures aimed at preventing discrimination of children with special needs, negative treatment of them is also reflected in the Law and documents.

Today, one of the important tasks of society is to take care of children with disabilities and create the necessary conditions for them to receive quality education, first of all, by introducing inclusive education. Inclusive education ensures that children with special needs receive education on the basis of equal rights with healthy children of normal development.

The international organization for the protection of children takes the rights of the child as its main goal in the Convention system. The idea of creating an education system that respects the rights and abilities of all children, taking into account the needs of all children, was put forward in

the Convention on the Rights of the Child. Because every child, whether he is healthy or has limited opportunities, has a unique character, interest, opportunity and need for knowledge.

An educational system that takes into account the needs of all children, respects their rights and abilities, and aims to achieve social justice and equality is called inclusive education.

Inclusive education is an educational process in which all children, regardless of their physical, mental, mental and other problems, are generally in their own home and territory, preschool educational organizations where all the conditions suitable for their needs are created, it means to study together with their peers in schools.

Inclusive education is the elimination of barriers (discrimination (differentiation)) between children with disabilities and healthy children, children who need special education, children with developmental disabilities (disabled for some reasons) , is an educational system that represents inclusion in the general education process, aimed at adapting to social life regardless of difficulties.

Inclusive education is based on the social model, which believes that the problem is not in the child, but in the program and methodology. This requires some changes to the education system. In this case, educational programs are prepared taking into account the needs of each child, the aspects of the methodology related to psychological problems are put on the right track. Inclusive education assumes that all children, including children with disabilities, can be educated in the educational institutions of their choice.

Inclusive education is much broader than formal education. This education mainly works with children with learning disabilities. What qualities should an inclusive school teacher and educator in an inclusive preschool educational organization have? Professional skills of the teacher are the main factor in inclusive education. First of all, the teacher must have an inclusive mindset and take responsibility for the quality of education. The main criteria for the quality of work of teachers in inclusive education is that the teacher protects and respects the rights of all children, despite the fact that students are of different categories.

Another quality is cooperation. Because cooperation and exchange of ideas is important for teachers. To systematically evaluate the teacher's performance, improve his/her regular skills, apply leadership and management skills, jointly solve problems, and establish comprehensive cooperation in order to effectively work with disciplinary and inter-institutional groups of children with special educational needs. It is necessary to have such qualities as 'yish'.

If special education is carried out according to mental and physical appearance, inclusive education is determined according to the child's abilities and capabilities. While special education is taught through special and alternative education programs, inclusive education is taught based on a child-centered and customized, instructional, inclusive curriculum. An important aspect of inclusive education is that children and teachers learn from each other and solve problems together. This education should not be one-sided. Family involvement is important in building self-confidence, developing skills and abilities, and encouraging learning from a young age in a child with disabilities. It is also important to work with parents in the process of inclusive education. It is worth noting that it is necessary to explain to parents with special needs that their children have the right to be a part of society, to convey this belief to their minds.

Education of disabled children, teaching them to read and write, helping them to adapt to social life is carried out on the basis of mutual cooperation between pedagogues and parents of disabled children.

There are two main factors for the involvement of children with disabilities in educational organizations: First, children with disabilities interact with healthy children, such children are protected from the social side, and healthy children are recognized for social justice and equality. they feel the importance of being more kind and considerate towards children with disabilities. Secondly, the fact that children with disabilities have the right to study and be educated side by side with their healthy peers.

Children with disabilities can work, study, learn a profession and develop at the level of their ability together with their healthy peers. If inclusive education is organized appropriately, children with disabilities are protected from the social side, feel that they have equal rights in social life, and that they can learn together with their peers.

Inclusive education can serve as a catalyst for improving the quality of education. Inclusive education helps prevent discrimination.

What results can be achieved if a child with disabilities is involved in inclusive education early:

- If he joins the neighborhood from childhood, he plays with the neighboring children, gets to know them, and begins to understand national values.

- In pre-school education, he learns to communicate with the people around him and his peers, the skills of self-service are formed from an early age.

- General secondary education is a period of success and confidence in the future for a child with disabilities. He continues to communicate with healthy people, realizes that he is faced with negative and positive views of others and finds his independent position in relation to them.

- When he steps into an independent life, he will be ready to study, work and participate in various relationships as an independent citizen. Parents and relatives are not worried about him going out.

- Those who know who he is and what he is capable of trust him when he joins society. As a result, he will have the opportunity to build a family and support his family.

So, if such a child is involved in inclusive education early, they will not be a burden to the society, but will be formed as an independent and active citizen.

On the basis of the above-mentioned points, education and upbringing of children with disabilities in educational institutions on the basis of equal rights is one of the important issues of today.

Experience shows that when we observe children with disabilities being integrated with healthy children in mass groups, children walking, in educational activities and various activities, healthy children dress differently than children with disabilities, wear shoes, they help in the walk with their sincere desire. Healthy and disabled children look at the pictures in the book together, learn to draw and count. In such a process, healthy children are brought up with qualities such as doing good to others, love, helping others, being responsible, friendship, and justice.

In conclusion, the development of an inclusive education strategy requires a long-term time. In order to develop this education, it is necessary to implement a step-by-step comprehensive approach to implementation.

The success of inclusive education, according to experts, depends on where children with disabilities go to study and the inclusive education program. First of all, inclusive education should be the work of the state and society, because people with special needs who do not have

the opportunity to receive education are excluded from the economic, social and political process. The state must provide them with equal opportunities. Talented and good specialists have grown up among disabled people who have received inclusive education.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi 23.09.2020 yildagi O‘RQ-637-sonli “Ta’lim to‘g‘risida”gi Qonuni
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi maktabgacha ta’lim tashkilotlari uchun ”Ilk qadam” davlat o‘quv dasturi, T- 2022 y.
3. Выгоцкий Л.С. Вопросы детской психологии.-М:С.П.Б.1999.
4. Белтоков В.И. Взаимодействие анализаторов в процессе восприятия и усвоения устной речи (в норми и паталогии)-М: Педагогика.1997.
5. Богдонова.Т .Г. Сурдопсихология-М. 2002.
6. Ҳайдарова Шахло Нарзуллаевна. Меҳрибонлик уйи тарбияланувчиларини оилавий ҳаётга тайёрлашнинг педагогик асослари. «SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS» Scientific Journal. VOLUME #1, ISSUE #1, 2020/XI. 149-154.
7. Haydarova Shaxlo Narzullaевна, (2021). Pedagogical Approach To The Preparation The Children Of The Orphanage For Family Life. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 3(02), 23-27.
8. Хайдарова Ш.Н. ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЙ ПОДХОД К ПОДГОТОВКЕ ВОСПИТАННИКОВ ДЕТСКОГО ДОМА К СЕМЕЙНОЙ ЖИЗНИ. Colloquium-journal №8 (95), 2021. Czesc 2. (Warszawa, Polska)
9. Ibraimov Kh. I. Creativity as one of the characteristics of the personality of the future teacher // Science, education and culture. – 2018. – no. 3 (27). - P. 44-46.
10. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal. - 2021. - P. 209-214.
11. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education 1 (2020): 6-15.
12. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).
13. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –T., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.
14. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
15. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
16. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
17. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.

18. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.
19. Ibragimov, X. I., U. A. Yo'ldoshev, and X. Bobomirzayev. "Pedagogik psixologiya." O'quv qo'llanma. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashiriyoti Toshkent (2009).